

Welcome to the EXA4MIND Newsletter

Who are we? We are a Horizon Europe project that aims to build an extreme data platform that brings together large scale data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures by implementing novel automated data management and effective data staging.

EXA4MIND Plenary Meeting in Prague

PLENARY MEETING

 **FEBRUARY
11 - 13**
 PRAGUE

Photo: CIIRC CTU/R. Sejkot.

From 11 to 13 February, the EXA4MIND consortium met in Prague, on the premises of the Czech Institute of Informatics, Robotics and Cybernetics ([CIIRC CTU](#)), for its plenary meeting. This was the first face-to-face consortium meeting of 2025, the third year of EXA4MIND, in which we will finalise many of our

developments. It was therefore a **very important plenary meeting** for the partners to review key issues for the development, implementation and materialisation of the EXA4MIND extreme data platform.

After these productive and enlightening days of face-to-face discussions, the consortium is more than ever ready to put all the knowledge and research of the last two years into action. Stay tuned as EXA4MIND will show its full potential in 2025.

[Discover more](#)

Scientific publications

Since the publication of our last newsletter, EXA4MIND has again been very active in publishing research papers and contributing to conferences. Below, we present a few **highlights** from these activities.

SCIENTIFIC
PUBLICATION

**Can We Ever
Develop an Ideal
RNA Force Field?
Lessons Learned
from Simulations
of the UUCG RNA
Tetraloop and
Other Systems**

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Can We Ever Develop an Ideal RNA Force Field? Lessons Learned from Simulations of the UUCG RNA Tetraloop and Other Systems

Authors: V. Mlýnský, P. Kührová, M. Pykal, M. Krepl, P. Stadlbauer, M. Otyepka, P. Banáš and J. Šponer.

Published in the [Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation](#).

Abstract: This study evaluates widely used pair-additive and polarisable RNA force fields (ffs) using the challenging UUCG tetraloop system. Standard MD simulations showed that most ffs failed to maintain the native state, except for three recent variants—OL3CP–gHBfix21, DES-Amber, and OL3R2.7—which preserved the desired structure. Enhanced sampling folding simulations of a shorter 8-mer UUCG TL revealed significant differences in estimated folding free energies. OL3CP–gHBfix21 produced values closest to experimental data, while DES-Amber and OL3R2.7 overestimated stability, suggesting inaccuracies in key interactions. Further testing on additional RNA and DNA systems confirmed performance issues. These findings underscore the challenges of accurately modeling RNA dynamics and highlight critical areas for future force field development.

This work was supported by EXA4MIND and it is part of the EXA4MIND Extreme Data processing platform.

Read it on our
website, [here](#)

SCIENTIFIC
PUBLICATION

Unsupervised Semantic Segmentation of Urban Scenes via Cross-Modal Distillation

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Unsupervised Semantic Segmentation of Urban Scenes via Cross-Modal Distillation

Authors: A. Vobecky, D. Hurych, O. Siméoni, S. Gidaris, A. Bursuc, P. Pérez and J. Sivic.

Published in the [International Journal of Computer Vision](#).

Abstract: Semantic image segmentation models typically require extensive pixel-wise annotations, which are costly to obtain and prone to biases. This work investigates learning semantic segmentation in urban scenes without any manual annotation. Researchers propose a novel method for learning pixel-wise semantic segmentation using raw, uncurated data from vehicle-mounted cameras and LiDAR sensors, thus eliminating the need for manual labelling. Researchers show the generalisation capabilities of their method by testing on four different testing datasets (Cityscapes, Dark Zurich, Nighttime Driving, and ACDC) without any fine-tuning. They present an in-depth experimental analysis of the proposed model including results when using another pre-training dataset, per-class and pixel accuracy results, confusion matrices, PCA visualisation, k-NN evaluation, ablations of the number of clusters and LiDAR's density, supervised fine-tuning as well as additional qualitative results and their analysis.

This research was carried out as part of the EXA4MIND industrial application case.

SCIENTIFIC
PUBLICATION

DocSpider: a Dataset of Cross- Domain Natural Language Querying for MongoDB

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DocSpider: a Dataset of Cross-Domain Natural Language Querying for MongoDB

Authors: A. G. Özer, R. F. Cekineli, I. H. Toroslu and P. Karagoz.

Published by [Cambridge University Press](#).

Abstract: Natural language querying allows users to formulate questions in a natural language without requiring specific knowledge of the database query language. Large language models have been very successful in addressing the text-to-SQL problem, which is about translating given questions in textual form into SQL statements. Document-oriented NoSQL databases are gaining popularity in the era of big data due to their ability to handle vast amounts of semi-structured data and provide advanced querying functionalities. However, studies on text-to-NoSQL systems, particularly on systems targeting document databases, are very scarce. This study uses large language models to create a cross-domain natural language to document database query dataset, DocSpider, leveraging the well-known text-to-SQL challenge dataset Spider. As a document database, the authors use MongoDB. Furthermore, they conduct experiments to assess the effectiveness of the DocSpider dataset to fine-tune a text-to-NoSQL model against a cross-

language transfer learning approach, SQL-to-NoSQL, and zero-shot instruction prompting. The experimental results reveal a significant improvement in the execution accuracy of fine-tuned language models when utilising the DocSpider dataset.

This work was supported by **EXA4MIND** and it is part of the EXA4MIND Extreme Data processing platform.

Read it on our
website, here

Campaign: Faces of EXA4MIND

With the **series "Faces of EXA4MIND"** we want to introduce the people who work every day to achieve our ambitious goal: Building a platform for Extreme Data that enables advanced data analytics on supercomputers and automated data management with support for integration by design with EOSC and European data spaces.

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FACES OF EXA4MIND

MEET THE PEOPLE BEHIND THE EXA4MIND PROJECT

WP6 - SME: HEALTHCARE APPLICATION CASE LEADER

RÉGIS CHEVALIER

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Régis Chevalier (Altrnativ)

We present Régis Chevalier from **Altrnativ**, and part of the Work Package 6 where our two SME application cases are coordinated — the Healthcare and the Viticulture application cases. On behalf of Altrnativ, he leads the **Healthcare application case**. *“EXA4MIND will positively impact healthcare by overcoming data silos and enabling the analysis of vast amounts of healthcare data through the integration of customised ETL tools. Its advanced extreme data processing*

capabilities and supercomputing resources will help unlock valuable insights to improve decision-making and patient care.”

[Read his interview](#)

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WP5 (INDUSTRY APPLICATION CASE) LEADER

DAVID HURYCH

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David Hurych (Valeo)

We present David Hurych from [Valeo](#) and WP5 ([Industry application case](#)) leader. When asked what makes this project special, he is clear about it: *“EXA4MIND will enable Valeo to efficiently process petabytes of real-world recordings and explore their contents by an untrained user. The developed tools and technologies will consequently lead to more efficient system validation, better planning of validation, captures recording, and increased safety of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems, which [Valeo develops](#).”*

[Watch his interview](#)

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